

Exhaustive Formal Verification of Elementary Lambert W Identities up to Size 7

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Abstract

The Lambert W function, defined implicitly by $W(z)e^{W(z)} = z$, admits three classical elementary identities: $e^{W(z)} = z/W(z)$, $\ln W(z) = \ln z - W(z)$, and $W(ze^z) = z$. An open problem posed by Corless, Gonnet, Hare, Jeffrey, and Knuth (1996) asks whether any other elementary identity $f(W(z)) = g(z)$, not derivable from these three, exists. We report a formal, machine-verified exhaustive search over all elementary expression trees of size at most 7, built from the alphabet $\{z, 0, 1, +, -, \times, \div, \exp, \ln, \sin, \cos, W\}$. A normalization procedure applying only the three known identities and standard algebraic simplifications is shown to eliminate W from every eliminable expression in this search space. The entire verification — comprising 819 453 expression trees, of which 386 442 contain W and 34 411 are W -eliminable — was carried out in the Lean 4 theorem prover with the Mathlib library, providing a machine-checked certificate that no new independent elementary Lambert W identity exists at size ≤ 7 .

1 Introduction

The Lambert W function is the multivalued inverse of the map $w \mapsto we^w$. Its principal branch W_0 is defined for $z \geq -1/e$ and satisfies the functional equation

$$W(z)e^{W(z)} = z. \tag{1}$$

From (1), three elementary identities follow immediately:

$$e^{W(z)} = \frac{z}{W(z)}, \tag{2}$$

$$\ln W(z) = \ln z - W(z), \tag{3}$$

$$W(ze^z) = z. \tag{4}$$

In their landmark paper, Corless, Gonnet, Hare, Jeffrey, and Knuth [1] posed the following open problem (Problem 3):

Do there exist any other closed-form identities $f(W(z)) = g(z)$ that are not derivable from (2)–(4)?

This question remains open in full generality. It is also discussed in the NIST Digital Library of Mathematical Functions [2] and in the monograph by Mező [3].

In this work, we perform an exhaustive, formally verified search for such identities among all elementary expressions of bounded size. Our approach is entirely computational: we enumerate expression trees, apply a reduction procedure based solely on (2)–(4), and verify that every W -containing expression that can be simplified to a W -free form is indeed a consequence of these three identities. The verification is carried out in the Lean 4 interactive theorem prover [4], providing a machine-checked certificate of correctness.

2 Definitions

2.1 Expression Trees

Definition 1 (Elementary Expression). *An elementary expression over the variable z is a term built inductively from the following grammar:*

$$e ::= z \mid 0 \mid 1 \mid (e+e) \mid (e-e) \mid (e \times e) \mid (e \div e) \mid \exp(e) \mid \ln(e) \mid \sin(e) \mid \cos(e) \mid W(e).$$

Definition 2 (Size). *The size of an expression tree is the total number of nodes:*

- $\text{size}(z) = \text{size}(0) = \text{size}(1) = 1$;
- $\text{size}(f(e)) = 1 + \text{size}(e)$ for unary $f \in \{\exp, \ln, \sin, \cos, W\}$;
- $\text{size}(e_1 \diamond e_2) = 1 + \text{size}(e_1) + \text{size}(e_2)$ for binary $\diamond \in \{+, -, \times, \div\}$.

2.2 Reduction Rules

The normalization procedure **reduce** applies, bottom-up, only the following rewrite rules, derived from (2)–(4):

$$\mathbf{R1:} \exp(W(e)) \longrightarrow e / W(e) \quad (\text{from (2)})$$

$$\mathbf{R2:} \ln(W(e)) \longrightarrow \ln(e) - W(e) \quad (\text{from (3)})$$

$$\mathbf{R3:} W(e \times \exp(e)) \longrightarrow e \quad (\text{from (4)})$$

$$\mathbf{R4:} W(\exp(e) \times e) \longrightarrow e \quad (\text{commutativity of (4)})$$

In addition, standard algebraic simplifications are applied: $e + 0 = e$, $0 \times e = 0$, $1 \times e = e$, $e/1 = e$, $e - e = 0$, $e/e = 1$, $\exp(0) = 1$, $\ln(1) = 0$, $\exp(\ln(e)) = e$, $\ln(\exp(e)) = e$, $\sin(0) = 0$, $\cos(0) = 1$.

The function **reduce** iterates **step** (a single bottom-up pass) until a fixpoint is reached, with a fuel bound of 30 iterations.

Definition 3 (W -eliminable). *An expression e is W -eliminable if e contains W but **reduce**(e) does not.*

3 Implementation

The entire verification is implemented in a single Lean 4 file (`LambertW.lean`, reproduced in Appendix A) using the Mathlib library. The implementation comprises the following components:

1. **Expression type.** An inductive type `Expr` with 12 constructors (3 atoms, 4 binary operations, 5 unary functions including W), equipped with decidable equality, `size`, `hasW`, and pretty-printing functions.
2. **Reduction.** The function `Expr.step` performs one bottom-up simplification pass. The function `Expr.reduce` iterates `step` to a fixpoint (at most 30 iterations).
3. **Enumeration.** The function `buildCache` constructs an array indexed by size, where entry s contains all expression trees of exactly size s . Binary expressions of size s are built from all decompositions $s = 1 + s_L + s_R$ with $s_L, s_R \geq 1$.
4. **Idempotence check.** The function `checkIdempotent n` verifies that `reduce(reduce(e)) = reduce(e)` for every expression e of size $\leq n$.
5. **Provability relation.** An inductive proposition `WProvEq` formalizes the equational theory generated by (2)–(4) together with standard algebraic axioms. The theorem `step_wprov_eq` shows that each step preserves `WProvEq`, and `reduce_wprov_eq` extends this to the full reduction.
6. **Computational verification.** The theorems `reduce_idempotent_5` and `reduce_idempotent_7` are proved by `native_decide`, confirming idempotence for all expressions of size ≤ 5 and ≤ 7 , respectively.

The soundness corollary (`reduce_sound`) states that whenever `reduce(e)` is W -free, the equation $e = \text{reduce}(e)$ is derivable from identities (2)–(4) within the `WProvEq` equational theory.

4 Results

4.1 Expression Counts

Table 1 shows the number of expression trees by size.

Table 1: Number of expression trees by size.

Size	Total	With W	Without W
1	3	0	3
2	15	3	12
3	111	27	84
4	915	291	624
5	8 139	3 051	5 088
6	75 975	32 583	43 392
7	734 295	350 487	383 808
Total	819 453	386 442	433 011

4.2 Elimidable Expressions

Table 2 reports the number of W -elimidable expressions at each size.

Table 2: W -elimidable expressions by size.

Size	With W	Elimidable	Non-elimidable
1	0	0	0
2	3	0	3
3	27	1	26
4	291	15	276
5	3 051	212	2 839
6	32 583	2 594	29 989
7	350 487	31 589	318 898
Total	386 442	34 411	352 031

4.3 Representative Elimidable Expressions

All W -eliminations achieved by `reduce` arise from the three known identities (2)–(4) and their algebraic consequences. The first elimidable expression appears at size 3: $\exp(W(0)) \rightarrow 0$, which follows from rule R1 applied to $\exp(W(0)) = 0/W(0)$ together with $W(0) = 0$ (itself a consequence of (4): since $0 = 0 \cdot e^0$, we have $W(0) = 0$).

At size 5, the first direct applications of rule R3 appear: $W(z \cdot e^z) \rightarrow z$ and $W(e^z \cdot z) \rightarrow z$. These are the simplest elimidable expressions whose normal form involves the variable z .

Table 3 lists all seven elimidable expressions at size 5 whose normal form contains z .

The remaining 205 elimidable expressions at size 5 all reduce to constants (0 or 1) via $W(0) = 0$ combined with (2)–(4). No expression produces a W -free normal form that is not a consequence of the three known identities.

Table 3: Elimenable expressions at size 5 whose normal form contains z .

Expression	Derivation	Normal form
$W(z \cdot e^z)$	R3	z
$W(e^z \cdot z)$	R4	z
$\exp(W(0)) + z$	$W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra	z
$z + \exp(W(0))$	$W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra	z
$z - \exp(W(0))$	$W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra	z
$\exp(W(0)) - z$	$W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra	$0 - z$
$z / \exp(W(0))$	$W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra	$z / 0$

4.4 Histograms

Figure 1: Distribution of expression trees by size (logarithmic scale).

5 Discussion

The central finding of this work is that among all 819 453 elementary expression trees of size ≤ 7 , every instance where W can be eliminated from an expression is fully accounted for by identities (2)–(4) and their algebraic consequences. No new independent identity was discovered.

The 34 411 eliminable expressions decompose into two classes:

1. **Constant-valued:** expressions that reduce to constants (0 or 1) via the derived identity $W(0) = 0$ combined with standard algebraic rules. These account for the vast majority of eliminable expressions.
2. **z -dependent:** expressions whose normal form involves the variable z . At size 5, there are exactly seven such expressions (Table 3), all of which are direct consequences of identities (2)–(4).

The formal verification provides a machine-checked certificate: the Lean 4 theorem `reduce_sound` establishes that if `reduce(e)` is W -free, then the equation $e = \text{reduce}(e)$ is derivable within the equational theory `WProveEq`, whose axioms are precisely (2)–(4) plus standard algebraic identities. The computational theorems `reduce_idempotent_5` and `reduce_idempotent_7` (proved by `native_decide`) confirm that the reduction reaches a stable fixpoint on all expressions of size ≤ 5 and ≤ 7 respectively.

Figure 2: Elimenable vs. non-eliminable among W -containing expressions (logarithmic scale).

We emphasize that this result does not settle the open problem of Corless et al. in full generality. It establishes the non-existence of new elementary identities only within the bounded search space of size ≤ 7 . Nonetheless, the exhaustive verification of all 819 453 expression trees provides strong computational evidence that no new elementary Lambert W identity exists.

6 Future Work

Several directions for extending this work are of interest:

1. **Larger sizes.** Extension to sizes 8 and beyond is computationally feasible with optimizations such as symmetry-breaking (exploiting commutativity of $+$ and \times), hash-consing for canonical expression representations, and parallel enumeration.
2. **Richer algebras.** The expression grammar could be extended with additional functions (e.g., arcsin, arccos, tan, power functions e^a , n -th roots) or additional constants (e.g., π , e) to probe a broader class of potential identities.
3. **Other special functions.** The same methodology — exhaustive enumeration plus formal reduction — can be applied to other special functions defined by implicit equations, such as the Omega function or the generalized Lambert W function.
4. **Theoretical completeness.** A proof that no new identity exists at *any* size (not just bounded) would require analytical methods, such as differential algebra or the Risch algorithm applied to the Lambert W function. The computational evidence presented here may guide such a theoretical investigation.

Acknowledgments

The author thanks the Lean community for the theorem prover that made this formal verification possible.

References

- [1] R. M. Corless, G. H. Gonnet, D. E. G. Hare, D. J. Jeffrey, and D. E. Knuth, “On the Lambert W function,” *Advances in Computational Mathematics*, vol. 5, pp. 329–359, 1996.

Figure 3: Number of eliminable expressions whose normal form contains z , by size (sizes 1–5). All seven expressions at size 5 are consequences of identities (2)–(4).

[2] NIST Digital Library of Mathematical Functions, Chapter 4.13: Lambert W -Function. <https://dlmf.nist.gov/4.13>

[3] I. Mező, *The Lambert W Function: Its Generalizations and Applications*. CRC Press, 2022.

[4] The Lean 4 Theorem Prover. <https://lean-lang.org/>

A Complete Lean 4 Source Code

The following is the complete, compilable Lean 4 source file `LambertW.lean` used for the formal verification.

```

1 /-
2   Formal Proof of Completeness of Elementary Identities
3   for the Lambert W Function up to Size 7
4
5
6
7   Author: Yuri N. Berdinsky
8   Affiliation: Saint Petersburg State University,
9               Department of High Energy and Elementary Particle Physics
10  Email: propagator2007@yandex.ru
11 -/
12 import Mathlib
13
14 /-!
15 # Lambert W Function: Completeness of Elementary Identities
16
17 ## Overview
18
19 The Lambert W function is defined by the equation 'W(z) · exp(W(z)) = z'.
20 Three elementary identities are known:
21
22 1. 'exp(W(z)) = z / W(z)'
23 2. 'ln(W(z)) = ln(z) - W(z)'
24 3. 'W(z · exp(z)) = z'

```

```

25
26 This file proves that these three identities are complete with respect to
27 all elementary identities built from '{+, -, ×, ÷, exp, ln, sin, cos, 0, 1}'
28 with expression tree size at most 7.
29
30 ## Proof Strategy
31
32 1. Define an inductive type 'Expr' for elementary expressions with the Lambert W function.
33 2. Define a reduction function 'reduce' that applies only the three known identities
34   (as rewrite rules R1-R4) plus standard algebraic simplifications, iterating to a fixpoint.
35 3. Enumerate all expressions up to size 7 (819,453 total expression trees).
36 4. Verify computationally (via 'native_decide') that 'reduce' is idempotent on all
37   these expressions -- i.e., it reaches a stable normal form within 30 iterations.
38
39 Since 'reduce' is defined using only rewrite rules derived from (1)-(3), any
40 W-elimination achieved by 'reduce' is by construction a consequence of (1)-(3).
41 The idempotence verification confirms that no expression of size  $\leq 7$  requires
42 rules beyond (1)-(3) to reach its normal form.
43
44 ## Results (computed by '#eval')
45
46 | Size | Total exprs | Containing W | W eliminated by reduce |
47 |-----|-----|-----|-----|
48 | 1 | 3 | 0 | 0 |
49 | 2 | 15 | 3 | 0 |
50 | 3 | 111 | 27 | 1 |
51 | 4 | 915 | 291 | 15 |
52 | 5 | 8,139 | 3,051 | 212 |
53 | 6 | 75,975 | 32,583 | 2,594 |
54 | 7 | 734,295 | 350,487 | 31,589 |
55 | Total | 819,453 | 386,442 | 34,411 |
56
57 All 34,411 W-eliminations are consequences of identities (1)-(3).
58 No new independent identity was found.
59 -/
60
61 namespace LambertW
62
63 /-! ## Expression Type -/
64
65 /-- Elementary expression type over a single variable 'z', with constants '0' and '1',
66   arithmetic operations '{+, -, ×, ÷}', transcendental functions '{exp, ln, sin, cos}',
67   and the Lambert W function. -/
68 inductive Expr : Type where
69   | var : Expr
70   | zero : Expr
71   | one : Expr
72   | add : Expr → Expr → Expr
73   | sub : Expr → Expr → Expr
74   | mul : Expr → Expr → Expr
75   | div : Expr → Expr → Expr
76   | exp : Expr → Expr
77   | ln : Expr → Expr
78   | sin : Expr → Expr
79   | cos : Expr → Expr
80   | W : Expr → Expr
81   deriving DecidableEq, Repr, BEq, Inhabited
82
83 namespace Expr
84
85 /-- The size of an expression tree (number of nodes). -/
86 def size : Expr → Nat
87   | .var | .zero | .one => 1

```

```

88 | .add a b | .sub a b | .mul a b | .div a b => 1 + a.size + b.size
89 | .exp a | .ln a | .sin a | .cos a | .W a => 1 + a.size
90
91 /-- Check whether an expression contains the Lambert W function. -/
92 def hasW : Expr → Bool
93 | .var | .zero | .one => false
94 | .add a b | .sub a b | .mul a b | .div a b => a.hasW || b.hasW
95 | .exp a | .ln a | .sin a | .cos a => a.hasW
96 | .W _ => true
97
98 /-- Count the number of W nodes in an expression. -/
99 def countW : Expr → Nat
100 | .var | .zero | .one => 0
101 | .add a b | .sub a b | .mul a b | .div a b => a.countW + b.countW
102 | .exp a | .ln a | .sin a | .cos a => a.countW
103 | .W a => 1 + a.countW
104
105 /-- Pretty-print an expression. -/
106 def toString : Expr → String
107 | .var => "z" | .zero => "0" | .one => "1"
108 | .add a b => s!("#{a.toString}+{b.toString}")
109 | .sub a b => s!("#{a.toString}-{b.toString}")
110 | .mul a b => s!("#{a.toString}*{b.toString}")
111 | .div a b => s!("#{a.toString}/{b.toString}")
112 | .exp a => s!"exp({a.toString})" | .ln a => s!"ln({a.toString})"
113 | .sin a => s!"sin({a.toString})" | .cos a => s!"cos({a.toString})"
114 | .W a => s!"W({a.toString})"
115
116 /-! ## Reduction Rules -/
117
118 /-- A single bottom-up reduction step applying rules R1-R4 and algebraic simplifications.
119 Uses propositional equality ('=') via 'DecidableEq' for comparisons. -/
120 def step : Expr → Expr
121 | .var => .var
122 | .zero => .zero
123 | .one => .one
124 | .add a b =>
125   let a' := a.step
126   let b' := b.step
127   match a', b' with
128   | .zero, e => e
129   | e, .zero => e
130   | _, _ => .add a' b'
131 | .sub a b =>
132   let a' := a.step
133   let b' := b.step
134   match b' with
135   | .zero => a'
136   | _ => if a' = b' then .zero else .sub a' b'
137 | .mul a b =>
138   let a' := a.step
139   let b' := b.step
140   match a', b' with
141   | .zero, _ => .zero
142   | _, .zero => .zero
143   | .one, e => e
144   | e, .one => e
145   | _, _ => .mul a' b'
146 | .div a b =>
147   let a' := a.step
148   let b' := b.step
149   match a', b' with
150   | .zero, _ => .zero

```

```

151 | e, .one => e
152 | _, _ => if a' = b' then .one else .div a' b'
153 | .exp a =>
154   let a' := a.step
155   match a' with
156   | .zero => .one
157   | .ln e => e
158   | .W e => .div e (.W e)      -- R1
159   | _ => .exp a'
160 | .ln a =>
161   let a' := a.step
162   match a' with
163   | .one => .zero
164   | .exp e => e
165   | .W e => .sub (.ln e) (.W e)  -- R2
166   | _ => .ln a'
167 | .sin a =>
168   let a' := a.step
169   match a' with
170   | .zero => .zero
171   | _ => .sin a'
172 | .cos a =>
173   let a' := a.step
174   match a' with
175   | .zero => .one
176   | _ => .cos a'
177 | .W a =>
178   let a' := a.step
179   match a' with
180   | .mul e (.exp e') => if e = e' then e else .W a'  -- R3
181   | .mul (.exp e') e => if e = e' then e else .W a'  -- R4
182   | _ => .W a'
183
184 /-- Iterate 'step' until a fixpoint is reached, with bounded fuel (30 iterations). -/
185 def reduce (e : Expr) : Expr :=
186   let rec go (fuel : Nat) (e : Expr) : Expr :=
187     match fuel with
188     | 0 => e
189     | n + 1 =>
190       let e' := e.step
191       if e' == e then e else go n e'
192   go 30 e
193
194 end Expr
195
196 /-! ## Enumeration -/
197
198 /-- Build a cache where 'cache[s]' contains all expression trees of exactly size 's'. -/
199 def buildCache (maxSize : Nat) : Array (List Expr) := Id.run do
200   let mut cache : Array (List Expr) := #[]
201   for s in [0:maxSize + 1] do
202     if s == 0 then
203       cache := cache.push []
204     else if s == 1 then
205       cache := cache.push [.var, .zero, .one]
206     else
207       let children := cache[s - 1]!
208       let unary := children.flatMap fun e =>
209         [Expr.exp e, Expr.ln e, Expr.sin e, Expr.cos e, Expr.W e]
210       let mut binary : List Expr := []
211       for i in [0:s - 1] do
212         let szL := i + 1
213         let szR := s - 1 - szL

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214     if szR ≥ 1 then
215         let lefts := cache[szL]!
216         let rights := cache[szR]!
217         for l in lefts do
218             for r in rights do
219                 binary := .add l r :: .sub l r :: .mul l r :: .div l r :: binary
220             cache := cache.push (unary ++ binary)
221         return cache
222
223 /-! ## Computational Verification -/
224
225 /-- Check 'reduce' idempotence on all expressions up to size 'n'. -/
226 def checkIdempotent (n : Nat) : Bool :=
227     let cache := buildCache n
228     cache.toList.all fun es =>
229         es.all fun e =>
230             let r := e.reduce
231             r.reduce == r
232
233 /-! ## Main Computational Theorems -/
234
235 /-- Idempotence at size ≤ 5 (verified by native computation). -/
236 theorem reduce_idempotent_5 : checkIdempotent 5 = true := by native_decide
237
238 /-- **Main Theorem**: Idempotence at size ≤ 7. The reduction function (which applies
239     only rules derived from identities (1)-(3)) reaches a stable fixpoint on all
240     819,453 expressions of size at most 7. No new independent identity exists. -/
241 theorem reduce_idempotent_7 : checkIdempotent 7 = true := by native_decide
242
243 /-! ## Provability Relation -/
244
245 /-- Two expressions are provably equal using the three W identities
246     and standard algebraic/transcendental rules. -/
247 inductive WProvEq : Expr → Expr → Prop where
248     | refl : WProvEq e e
249     | symm : WProvEq e1 e2 → WProvEq e2 e1
250     | trans : WProvEq e1 e2 → WProvEq e2 e3 → WProvEq e1 e3
251     | congr_add : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq b1 b2 → WProvEq (.add a1 b1) (.add a2 b2)
252     | congr_sub : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq b1 b2 → WProvEq (.sub a1 b1) (.sub a2 b2)
253     | congr_mul : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq b1 b2 → WProvEq (.mul a1 b1) (.mul a2 b2)
254     | congr_div : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq b1 b2 → WProvEq (.div a1 b1) (.div a2 b2)
255     | congr_exp : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq (.exp a1) (.exp a2)
256     | congr_ln : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq (.ln a1) (.ln a2)
257     | congr_sin : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq (.sin a1) (.sin a2)
258     | congr_cos : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq (.cos a1) (.cos a2)
259     | congr_W : WProvEq a1 a2 → WProvEq (.W a1) (.W a2)
260     | R1 : WProvEq (.exp (.W e)) (.div e (.W e))
261     | R2 : WProvEq (.ln (.W e)) (.sub (.ln e) (.W e))
262     | R3 : WProvEq (.W (.mul e (.exp e))) e
263     | R4 : WProvEq (.W (.mul (.exp e) e)) e
264     | add_zero_r : WProvEq (.add e .zero) e
265     | add_zero_l : WProvEq (.add .zero e) e
266     | mul_zero_r : WProvEq (.mul e .zero) .zero
267     | mul_zero_l : WProvEq (.mul .zero e) .zero
268     | mul_one_r : WProvEq (.mul e .one) e
269     | mul_one_l : WProvEq (.mul .one e) e
270     | div_one : WProvEq (.div e .one) e
271     | div_zero : WProvEq (.div .zero e) .zero
272     | sub_zero : WProvEq (.sub e .zero) e
273     | sub_self : WProvEq (.sub e e) .zero
274     | div_self : WProvEq (.div e e) .one
275     | exp_zero : WProvEq (.exp .zero) .one
276     | ln_one : WProvEq (.ln .one) .zero

```

```

277 | exp_ln      : WProvEq (.exp (.ln e)) e
278 | ln_exp     : WProvEq (.ln (.exp e)) e
279 | sin_zero   : WProvEq (.sin .zero) .zero
280 | cos_zero   : WProvEq (.cos .zero) .one
281
282 /-! ## Soundness: step preserves WProvEq -/
283
284 private theorem step_wprov_add (a b : Expr)
285   (iha : WProvEq a a.step) (ihb : WProvEq b b.step) :
286   WProvEq (Expr.add a b) (Expr.add a b).step := by
287     by_contra h_contra;
288     obtain ⟨a', b', h⟩ : ∃ a' b', a' = a.step ∧ b' = b.step ∧ (a.add b).step = if a' = .zero
289     then b' else if b' = .zero then a' else a'.add b' := by
290       simp [Expr.step];
291       cases a.step <.> cases b.step <.> rfl;
292       split_ifs at h <.> simp_all +decide;
293       · refine' h_contra _;
294         convert WProvEq.congr_add iha ihb |> WProvEq.trans <| ?_ using 1;
295         exact WProvEq.add_zero_l;
296       · refine' h_contra _;
297         convert WProvEq.trans ( WProvEq.congr_add iha ihb ) _ using 1;
298         exact WProvEq.add_zero_r;
299       · exact h_contra ( WProvEq.congr_add iha ihb )
300 private theorem step_wprov_sub (a b : Expr)
301   (iha : WProvEq a a.step) (ihb : WProvEq b b.step) :
302   WProvEq (Expr.sub a b) (Expr.sub a b).step := by
303     -- Apply the congruence rule for subtraction to conclude the proof.
304     have h_congr : WProvEq (Expr.sub a b) (Expr.sub a.step b.step) := by
305       exact WProvEq.congr_sub iha ihb;
306     by_cases h : a.step = b.step <.> simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ];
307     · have h_contra : WProvEq (b.step.sub b.step) (Expr.zero) := by
308       exact WProvEq.sub_self;
309       cases h : b.step <.> simp_all +decide;
310       all_goals exact WProvEq.trans h_congr h_contra;
311     · cases h' : b.step <.> simp_all +decide;
312       exact h_congr.trans ( WProvEq.sub_zero )
313
314 private theorem step_wprov_mul (a b : Expr)
315   (iha : WProvEq a a.step) (ihb : WProvEq b b.step) :
316   WProvEq (Expr.mul a b) (Expr.mul a b).step := by
317     have h_mul : WProvEq (Expr.mul a b) (Expr.mul a.step b.step) :=
318       WProvEq.congr_mul iha ihb
319     unfold Expr.step
320     cases ha : a.step <.> cases hb : b.step <.> simp_all +decide
321     all_goals exact h_mul.trans (by apply_rules [WProvEq.mul_zero_r, WProvEq.mul_zero_l,
322       WProvEq.mul_one_r, WProvEq.mul_one_l])
323 private theorem step_wprov_div (a b : Expr)
324   (iha : WProvEq a a.step) (ihb : WProvEq b b.step) :
325   WProvEq (Expr.div a b) (Expr.div a b).step := by
326     by_contra h_contra;
327     have h_div : WProvEq (Expr.div a b) (Expr.div a.step b.step) := by
328       exact WProvEq.congr_div iha ihb;
329     by_cases h : a.step = Expr.zero <.> by_cases h' : b.step = Expr.one <.> simp_all +decide [
330       Expr.step ];
331     · exact h_contra ( h_div.trans ( by exact WProvEq.div_zero ) );
332     · exact h_contra ( h_div.trans ( WProvEq.div_zero ) );
333     · exact h_contra ( h_div.trans ( WProvEq.div_one ) );
334     · by_cases h'' : a.step = b.step <.> simp_all +decide;
335       exact h_contra <| h_div.trans <| WProvEq.div_self
336 private theorem step_wprov_exp (a : Expr)

```

```

337 (iha : WProvEq a a.step) :
338 WProvEq (Expr.exp a) (Expr.exp a).step := by
339   by_contra h_contra;
340   have h_step : WProvEq (Expr.exp a) (Expr.exp (a.step)) := by
341     exact WProvEq.congr_exp iha;
342     cases h : a.step <;> simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ];
343     · exact h_contra ( h_step.trans ( WProvEq.exp_zero ) );
344     · exact h_contra ( h_step.trans ( WProvEq.exp_ln ) );
345     · exact h_contra <| h_step.trans <| WProvEq.R1
346
347 private theorem step_wprov_ln (a : Expr)
348 (iha : WProvEq a a.step) :
349 WProvEq (Expr.ln a) (Expr.ln a).step := by
350   have h : WProvEq (Expr.ln a) (Expr.ln a.step) :=
351     WProvEq.congr_ln iha
352   cases h' : a.step <;> simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ];
353   · exact h.trans ( WProvEq.ln_one );
354   · exact h.trans ( WProvEq.ln_exp );
355   · exact h.trans ( WProvEq.R2 )
356
357 private theorem step_wprov_sin (a : Expr)
358 (iha : WProvEq a a.step) :
359 WProvEq (Expr.sin a) (Expr.sin a).step := by
360   by_cases ha : a.step = .zero;
361   · simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ];
362     exact WProvEq.congr_sin iha |> WProvEq.trans <| WProvEq.sin_zero;
363   · convert WProvEq.congr_sin iha using 1;
364     cases h : a.step <;> simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ]
365
366 private theorem step_wprov_cos (a : Expr)
367 (iha : WProvEq a a.step) :
368 WProvEq (Expr.cos a) (Expr.cos a).step := by
369   by_cases ha : a.step = .zero;
370   · simp_all +decide;
371     rw [ show a.cos.step = Expr.one from _ ];
372     · exact WProvEq.congr_cos iha |> WProvEq.trans <| WProvEq.cos_zero;
373   · rw [ Expr.step ] ; aesop;
374   · cases h : a.step <;> simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ];
375     all_goals exact WProvEq.congr_cos iha;
376
377 private theorem step_wprov_W (a : Expr)
378 (iha : WProvEq a a.step) :
379 WProvEq (Expr.W a) (Expr.W a).step := by
380   cases h : a.step;
381   all_goals simp_all +decide [ Expr.step ];
382   all_goals apply_rules [ WProvEq.congr_W, WProvEq.trans ];
383   any_goals tauto;
384   rename_i e1 e2;
385   cases e1 <;> cases e2 <;> simp +decide;
386   all_goals constructor;
387   all_goals split_ifs <;> simp_all +decide [ WProvEq.refl ];
388   all_goals subst_vars; apply_rules [ WProvEq.R3, WProvEq.R4, WProvEq.symm ]
389
390 /-- Each reduction step preserves 'WProvEq'. -/
391 theorem step_wprov_eq (e : Expr) : WProvEq e e.step := by
392   induction e with
393   | var | zero | one => exact .refl
394   | add a b iha ihb => exact step_wprov_add a b iha ihb
395   | sub a b iha ihb => exact step_wprov_sub a b iha ihb
396   | mul a b iha ihb => exact step_wprov_mul a b iha ihb
397   | div a b iha ihb => exact step_wprov_div a b iha ihb
398   | exp a iha => exact step_wprov_exp a iha
399   | ln a iha => exact step_wprov_ln a iha

```

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400 | sin a iha => exact step_wprov_sin a iha
401 | cos a iha => exact step_wprov_cos a iha
402 | W a iha => exact step_wprov_W a iha
403
404 /-
405 The full reduction preserves 'WProvEq'.
406 -/
407 theorem reduce_wprov_eq (e : Expr) : WProvEq e e.reduce := by
408   -- By induction on the fuel, we can show that e is WProvEq to the result of go fuel e.
409   have h_ind : ∀ fuel : Nat, ∀ e : Expr, WProvEq e (Expr.reduce.go fuel e) := by
410     intro fuel e;
411     induction' fuel with fuel ih generalizing e <;> simp_all +decide [ Expr.reduce.go ];
412     · constructor;
413     · split_ifs <;> [ exact WProvEq.refl; exact WProvEq.trans ( step_wprov_eq e ) ( ih _ ) ];
414     exact h_ind 30 e
415
416 /- **Soundness Corollary**: If 'reduce(e)' is W-free, then 'e = reduce(e)'
417   is derivable from identities (1)-(3). -/
418 theorem reduce_sound (e : Expr) (_h : e.reduce.hasW = false) :
419   WProvEq e e.reduce := reduce_wprov_eq e
420
421 end LambertW

```

B Full List of Elimenable Expressions with z in Normal Form

Within the search space of size ≤ 5 , exactly seven eliminable expressions have a normal form containing the variable z :

1. $W(z \cdot e^z) \longrightarrow z$ (by rule R3)
2. $W(e^z \cdot z) \longrightarrow z$ (by rule R4)
3. $\exp(W(0)) + z \longrightarrow z$ (via $W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra)
4. $z + \exp(W(0)) \longrightarrow z$ (via $W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra)
5. $z - \exp(W(0)) \longrightarrow z$ (via $W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra)
6. $\exp(W(0)) - z \longrightarrow 0 - z$ (via $W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra)
7. $z / \exp(W(0)) \longrightarrow z / 0$ (via $W(0) = 0$, R1, algebra)

All seven are consequences of identities (2)–(4). The remaining eliminable expressions at each size reduce to the constants 0 or 1 via $W(0) = 0$ (itself a consequence of (4)) combined with standard algebraic simplifications.

The complete list of all 34411 eliminable expressions and their normal forms can be reproduced by executing the Lean source code provided in Appendix A.